

Open Media @ UGA

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Overview

- ◀ Introduction to BMA
- ◀ AV Digitization at the Brown Media Archives
- ◀ Strategies for Implementing Change
- ◀ Future of Open Source at BMA

About BMA Collections

- ▶ University of Georgia
- ▶ Collections divided into 3 categories:
 - ▶ Newsfilm (6 Georgia stations)
 - ▶ Peabody Awards Collection
 - ▶ "Other" (home movies, UGA athletics, interview collections, folklore, town films, etc.)
- ▶ 250,000+ physical items (mostly video), over a petabyte of digital content

UGA Special Collections Library

- ▶ Moved into new building in 2012
- ▶ One of three departments in SCL
- ▶ 30,000 sq ft, high density storage vault

What's missing from this list?

The new Special Collections Libraries Building contains:

- Integrated security
- Customized climate control
- Galleries for exhibits
- Classrooms to integrate archival materials into instruction
- Space for colloquia and other events
- Growth for 40 years

(from a description of SCL building written around the time the building was opened in 2012)

vs.

History of AV Digitization at Brown Media Archives

3 Eras

- ▶ The James Era (2007-2012)
 - ▶ Digitization begins, "industry" trends
- ▶ The Alex Era (2012-2016)
 - ▶ Move towards open source
- ▶ And Now (2016-present)

Pre-historic (1995-2007)

- ▶ Not much digitization for first ~10 years

The James Era (2007-2012)

- ◀ Mid-2000s: two grants kick-started AV digitization
 - ◀ Civil Rights Digital Library (film)
 - ◀ Local TV in Peabody Awards Collection (3/4-inch U-matic)
 - ◀ SAMMA machines: produced MXF-wrapped J2K files

The James Era (2007-2012) [cont.]

- ▶ Only person "doing" digitization / digital preservation at BMA
- ▶ Kept the in-house digitization going after grants
- ▶ Video production background = v. aware of "industry trends"
- ▶ Lot of MOV wrapped files
 - ▶ DV, shifted to ProRes
- ▶ Mac computers (uncommon)
 - ▶ Final Cut Pro

The Alex Era (2012-2016)

- ◀ Shift to more open source solutions begins
- ◀ Demand for collections increases
- ◀ Still only one full time staff member
- ◀ 2015: First "Digital Archivist" hired
 - ◀ "Professional" vs. "Paraprofessional" in academic libraries in US
- ◀ Scaling up infrastructure, automating processes
 - ◀ ffmpeg, mediainfo
 - ◀ automated scripting (bash and Python) for transcoding, checksums

The Alex Era (2012-2016) [cont.]

- ▶ Purchased a film scanner
 - ▶ DPX files galore
 - ▶ Storage needs increase
- ▶ Introduction of CollectiveAccess to manage analog and digital media
 - ▶ "open source" baggage

A Fast Moving Train

Increasing Demand & Output

Requests for our collections have increased exponentially since 2012. Produce about 2 TB / week

Folders with Files

Is X digitized? Do we have an HD version of that? Was this supposed to have audio?

Digital/LTO backlog

About a dozen LTO3 tapes, about 1000 LTO5 tapes (currently using LTO7)

Access

At least 5 *totally different* ways of providing access to digital content to end users

Spotty Documentation

Undocumented (or minimally documented) workflows, policies, and procedures.

Other Duties as Assigned...

CollectiveAccess, supporting teaching mission of university, coordinating with Peabody Office, University committees, etc. etc.

Two Conflicting Realities

Truth #1

We need better workflows, better tools, better infrastructure: a more manageable system.

Truth #2

It is hard to find the time to make these changes when feeling overwhelmed by the existing flow of work.

Strategies for

[Attempting to Maybe Try and Figure Out
How To Go About]

Implementing Change

Strategy #1: Find a community

- ◀ Digital Curation Working Group: charged with developing policies for ARCHive digital preservation system
- ◀ Evolved into lib-learn-tech group at UGA Libraries
 - ◀ "Community of Practice"
 - ◀ XSLT, bash scripting, Python
 - ◀ Getting UGA Libs IT/Systems involved
- ◀ Unifying workflows across departments

Strategy #2: Internal Outsourcing

- ▶ Asking coworkers who aren't necessarily even in your department to help you with things
- ▶ Difficult to let go of sweet lil' nugget problems
- ▶ Examples:
 - ▶ XSL style sheets, Python-izing AIP-prep scripts, renaming PDFs, batch ffmpeg conversions

Strategy #3: Challenge = Opportunity

- ▶ DPX files (does anyone like these?)
 - ▶ Difficulties getting files on/off of LTO
 - ▶ False positive with virus-scanning software
 - ▶ Malformed bags
- ▶ J2K files from SAMMA
- ▶ All the more reason to shift to MKV/FFV1

"It is broken. We should definitely fix it."

Strategy #4: Seize the Moment

- ▶ NHPRC grant to preserve 4000 hours of public broadcasting content from Peabody Awards Collection to become part of AAPB (American Archive of Public Broadcasting)
- ▶ Benefits of Bureaucracy
 - ▶ Putting the grant out for open bidding = opportunity to redo technical specifications for deliverables

Strategy #5: Lean on Yall

- ▶ Ruthlessly steal other people's workflows/specs
- ▶ AMIA Open Source
- ▶ ffmpeg: Thank you ffmprovisr!

*Everyone in this room who writes blog posts, puts their workflow online, pushes scripts to github, responds to my Twitter Qs: **Thank you!***

Moments yet to be Seized

Open Source plans for the
future

Become the Tipping Point

- ▶ FFV1 / MKV for film scans: RAWcooked
- ▶ Using MKV chapter feature for newsfilm?
- ▶ MediaConch
- ▶ Figure out how to give \$ support to open source projects

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